

POLICY FRAMEWORK FOR ADVANCING DIGITAL INCLUSION IN UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA: EXTENT OF AWARENESS, IMPLEMENTATION AND CHALLENGES

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Received: Jun 10, 2025

Accepted: Jul 11 2025

Published: Sep 20, 2025

Abstract

The study examined policy framework for advancing digital inclusion in universities in South-South, Nigeria with special attention on the extent of awareness, implementation and challenges. It followed a qualitative approach with 3 research questions provided answers for in the study. Survey descriptive research design was adopted to provide the right blueprint for the study. Sample size of 678 lecturers was used for the study through convenience non-randomized sampling technique. An online structured questionnaire, titled 'Questionnaire for Awareness, Implementation and Challenges in Policy Framework for Digital Inclusion (QAICPFDI)' was used for data collection, after being validated by 3 Digital Economy experts from 3 universities. Cronbach alpha technique was adopted to test reliability of the instrument, and coefficients of 0.81 was obtained, and deemed satisfactory. The instrument was administered online through different WhatsApp platforms of academic staff in public universities in South-South, Nigeria, and the data was analyzed using simple arithmetic mean. Findings from the study revealed that

the extent of awareness on the available digital inclusion policies, as well as its implementation is low. The study also found that the challenges limiting digital inclusion from being effectively implemented include but are not limited to: limited internet and power infrastructure, high cost of internet and devices, low digital literacy levels, and inadequacy of policy implementation. The study concluded that this is a big setback in pursuit of the digital inclusion limitlessly. It was recommended that there should be provision of required supportive infrastructure and resources, such as skilled trainers, functional internet facilities, steady power supply, adequate funds for procurement, distribution and operations of digital inclusion programmes, and continuity in programme implementations.

Keywords: Policy, Digital, Inclusion, Awareness, Implementation, Challenges.

Introduction and Statement of the problem

In the 21st century, digital technologies have transformed the landscape of education, making access to digital tools and internet connectivity essential for learning, research, and innovation. Universities, as centers of knowledge production and dissemination, play a crucial role in driving digital transformation. In Nigeria, digital inclusion remains a significant challenge due to disparities in ICT access, digital literacy, and infrastructure availability. Supporting this, Eke, Uche and Adeniran (2022) posited that to advance digital inclusion in Nigerian universities, a robust policy framework is essential, requiring government agencies, university administrators, private sector players, and international organizations to collaborate to improve ICT infrastructure, enhance digital literacy, and make digital tools more affordable and accessible. Achieving this requires a well-structured policy framework to provide a structured set of principles, strategies, and guidelines that guide decision-making and implementation in a specific area. This implies that a policy framework serves as a blueprint and manual guide for digital

inclusion, in terms of increasing access to digital resources, improving ICT infrastructure, promoting digital literacy, and ensuring affordability in educational institutions in Nigeria in general, and South-South in particular.

Digital inclusion is about providing all supportive mechanisms to motivate and ensure that digital enthusiasts of backgrounds and diversities are provided with the opportunities to be fully involved in the digital economy in the area of learning, employment and utilization of digital infrastructure for the betterment of the society. Similarly, Awoleye and Siyanbola (2019) described digital inclusion as the ability of individuals and communities to access and effectively use information and communication technologies (ICTs) to enhance their learning, employment, and civic participation. Throwing more light into this, Jacob, Somadina and Olatunde-Aiyedun (2021) buttressed that digital inclusion is multidimensional concept that encompasses availability of ICT infrastructure, affordability and accessibility, digital literacy and capacity building, and policy and institutional support. In relation to the university system in Nigeria, especially in South-South, this might mean ensuring that universities have stable broadband connectivity, computing devices, and digital platforms, affordable access to the internet, digital learning tools, and online educational resources, equipping students and faculty with the necessary skills to engage in the digital economy, and establishing legal and institutional frameworks to support digital learning initiatives that accommodate limitless diversities of digital enthusiasts. Digital inclusion refers to efforts aimed at ensuring equitable access to digital technologies, the internet, and ICT skills for all individuals, regardless of their socioeconomic background, geographic location, or physical abilities (OECD, 2019). In the university setting, it means enabling students, lecturers, and researchers to utilize digital resources effectively for academic and professional growth.

A policy is a set of rules, guidelines, and strategic actions that governments or institutions implement to achieve specific objectives. In the context of digital inclusion, policies outline strategies for expanding ICT infrastructure, promoting e-learning, and ensuring that disadvantaged groups have equal access to digital tools. It is in recognition of the importance of digital inclusion that Nigerian Government has developed several policies to promote it, such as the National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) 2020–2030, and the National Broadband Plan (2020–2025), et cetera (Nwosu, 2020). The goal is to promote digital literacy and skill development, and to improve internet penetration, particularly in educational institutions. There is no doubt that the benefits of digital inclusion abound, provided the mechanisms to tapping into its gains are effectively exploited. This is the more reason government and non-governmental agencies have continued to work towards institutionalizing digital inclusion the policies and strategic measures.

Despite these initiatives, awareness and implementation remain inconsistent across Nigeria. Nwosu (2020) observed that while some private universities and institutions in urban areas have integrated digital learning systems, many public universities, especially in rural areas, face severe infrastructural deficits. Research shows that a significant percentage of students and faculty members are unaware of existing digital inclusion policies and lack the digital skills necessary to maximize available technology (Masimbe, 2019). To compound the situation is the noticeable inadequacy of digital technological infrastructure, such as lack stable broadband connectivity, modern ICT laboratories, and reliable electricity to support digital learning (Oladipupo & Abdulazeez, 2024). There seem to also exist the issue of high cost of data, laptops, and digital tools, making unaffordable for many students and lecturers, with the consequences of being cut off from digital practices (Awoleye & Siyanbola, 2019). Furthermore, Nwosu (2020);

Olumide and Adegbite (2023) lamented that while policies exist, enforcement remains weak due to bureaucratic bottlenecks, corruption, and inadequate funding many students and educators, with some students and lecturers' lack the necessary digital skills to utilize technology effectively in learning and research further causing some setbacks. In other to add to existing literature in a manner that is peculiar to universities in South-South, Nigeria, the study examined policy framework for advancing digital inclusion with emphasis on the extent of awareness, implementation and challenges.

Research Question

The following research questions were provided answers for in the study:

1. What is the extent of awareness of the available policies put in place for the advancement of digital inclusion in universities in South-South, Nigeria?
2. To what extent are the digital inclusion policies being implemented in universities in South-South, Nigeria?
3. What are the challenges limiting digital inclusion policies from being effectively implemented in universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Research Method

The survey descriptive research design was adopted to provide the right blueprint for the study. The survey descriptive research design is considered as one of the research design procedures in which a researcher administers a data collection instrument (online and or offline) on a sample or to the entire population of people, known as respondents, in order to elicit relevant data that could aid in describing and providing systematic explanations to the attitudes, opinions, behaviours and or characteristics of the population on a matter being studied (Tanny, 2018). The design is considered suitable and appropriate for the investigation because the study

intends to collect data from a sample of lecturers on matters relating to awareness, implementation and challenges in policy framework and digital inclusion, using a structured questionnaire as the major instrument of survey.

The targeted population of the study was all the lecturers in all the public universities in South-South, Nigeria. The sample size of 678 lecturers was used for the study through the convenience non-randomized sampling technique. Convenience sampling is considered as one of the sampling strategies in qualitative research that involves allowing potential respondents to respond to data collection instrument(s) based on their willingness, availability, accessibility and commitment to ensuring data is genuinely collected (Orji, 2025). This technique was considered suitable because the survey was conducted online, and quite a number of lecturers are thought to be skeptical about online surveys.

An online structured questionnaire, titled “Questionnaire for Awareness, Implementation and Challenges in Policy Framework for Digital Inclusion (QAICPFDI)” was used for data collection. The instrument was developed based on review of related literature and consultation of experts in digital economy. The instrument was structured into two sections, namely: Sections A and B. Section A focused on personal information of the lecturer, such as name of the university. Section B has 30 items related to awareness, implementation and challenges in policy framework for digital inclusion. It was structured on four points rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with weighted points: 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The validation of the instrument ‘Questionnaire for Awareness, Implementation and Challenges in Policy Framework for Digital Inclusion (QAICPFDI)’ was determined through the help of three Digital Economy experts in 3 universities. It was mailed to the experts, along with

the research questions and design of the statement, who were requested to examine and scrutinize the items in terms of contents, relevance, suitability, clarity and scope. Their inputs were taken into account before the final development and online administration. For the data used for computing the reliability indices, the instrument was pilot-administered on 50 lecturers from public universities in South-East, Nigeria. The Cronbach alpha technique was adopted with the reliability coefficients of 0.81 obtained, and the instrument ascertained reliable for the study. This is in line with Nworgu (2015) who recommended that co-efficient value of 0.60 and above is adequate for any research work.

The instrument, ‘Questionnaire for Awareness, Implementation and Challenges in Policy Framework for Digital Inclusion (QAICPFDI)’ was administered online through different WhatsApp platforms of academic staff in public universities in South-South, Nigeria. This was made possible through the help of lecturer colleagues and friends at various public universities in the targeted region who aided in explaining the need for the study, ensuring some lecturers’ willingness to be fill out the questionnaire. After two weeks of the online survey, 678 responses were successfully retrieved, and used for the data analysis. The data was analyzed using simple arithmetic mean for the research question. In answering the research question, any mean rating that falls below 2.50 was remarked as not agreed while any mean rating of 2.50 or above was remarked agreed.

Presentation and Interpretation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the extent of awareness of the available policies put in place for the advancement of digital inclusion in universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean ratings of lecturers on the extent of awareness of the available policies put in place for the advancement of digital inclusion in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

S/N	Items: Extent of awareness of policies put in place for the advancement of digital inclusion	Male (n=678)		Female (n=678)	
		Mean	Remark	Mean	Remark
1.	National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) which was launched to transform Nigeria into a leading digital economy	2.48	Disagreed	2.40	Disagreed
2.	National Digital Learning Policy which is meant for policy direction and general guidelines, digital learning platforms development, local digital content provisioning, infrastructure and access devices, and capacity building	2.46	Disagreed	2.44	Disagreed
3.	Universal Service Provision Fund (USPF) aimed at facilitating the achievement of national policy goals for universal access and service to ICTs in rural, unserved, and underserved areas in Nigeria	2.49	Disagreed	2.42	Disagreed
4.	NITDA Digital State Initiative with focus on training Nigerian youths aged 16 to 40 in digital literacy and skills, covering areas such as digital marketing, productivity tools, and content creation	2.60	Agreed	2.64	Agreed
5.	Digital Financial Services Policy aimed at bringing unserved and underserved Nigerians into the formal financial sector through technology	2.64	Agreed	2.50	Agreed
6.	National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act, 2007 for the ICT policy implementing arm of the Federal Ministry of Communications, Innovation, and Digital Economy	2.51	Agreed	2.66	Agreed
7.	National Broadband Plan aimed at increasing broadband penetration across the country; ensuring that more Nigerians have access to high-speed internet, which is crucial for digital inclusion	2.49	Disagreed	2.46	Disagreed
8.	ICT in Education Policy which focuses on embedding ICT into the educational system to enhance learning and teaching processes	2.56	Agreed	2.60	Agreed
9.	Digital Rights and Freedom Bill, although not yet enacted into law, it seeks to protect the digital rights of Nigerians, promoting freedom of expression and privacy online	2.01	Disagreed	2.07	Disagreed

10.	National e-Government Master Plan aimed at digitizing government operations and services; making them more accessible to citizens and promoting digital literacy and inclusion	2.03	Disagreed	2.00	Disagreed
	Cluster Mean	2.43		2.42	

Table 1 shows that items 1, 2, 3, 7, 9 and 10 are remarked ‘disagreed’ which in this study implied to a ‘low extent’. The mean ratings of these items ranges from 2.00 to 2.49 and are less than the 2.5 acceptance benchmark. This means that the extent of awareness of the existence of digital inclusion policies, namely: National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS); National Digital Learning Policy; Universal Service Provision Fund (USPF); National Broadband Plan; Digital Rights and Freedom Bill, and National e-Government Master Plan is low. Meanwhile, the respondents agreed to be highly aware of digital inclusion policies on items 4, 5, 6 and 8, and the mean rating of each of these items is greater than or equal to 2.5, which is the acceptable benchmark. The items with high extent ratings are: Digital Financial Services Policy; National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act, 2007; ICT in Education Policy, and NITDA Digital State Initiative.

Research Question 2: To what extent are the digital inclusion policies being implemented in universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean ratings of lecturers on the extent to which digital inclusion policies are being implemented in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

S/N	Items: The extent of implementation of digital inclusion policies	Male (n=678)		Female (n=678)	
		Mean	Remark	Mean	Remark
1.	National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) which was launched to transform Nigeria into a leading digital economy	2.51	Agreed	2.54	Agreed
2.	National Digital Learning Policy which is meant for policy direction and general guidelines, digital learning platforms development, local digital content provisioning, infrastructure and access devices, and capacity building	2.48	Disagreed	2.48	Disagreed
3.	Universal Service Provision Fund (USPF) aimed at facilitating the achievement of national policy goals for universal access and service to ICTs in rural, unserved, and underserved areas in Nigeria	2.49	Disagreed	2.45	Disagreed
4.	NITDA Digital State Initiative with focus on training Nigerian youths aged 16 to 40 in digital literacy and skills, covering areas such as digital marketing, productivity tools, and content creation	2.50	Agreed	2.58	Agreed
5.	Digital Financial Services Policy aimed at bringing unserved and underserved Nigerians into the formal financial sector through technology	2.43	Disagreed	2.48	Disagreed
6.	National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act, 2007 for the ICT policy implementing arm of the Federal Ministry of Communications, Innovation, and Digital Economy	2.46	Disagreed	2.49	Disagreed
7.	National Broadband Plan aimed at increasing broadband penetration across the country; ensuring that more Nigerians have access to high-speed internet, which is crucial for digital inclusion	2.54	Agreed	2.52	Agreed
8.	ICT in Education Policy which focuses on embedding ICT into the educational system to enhance learning and teaching processes	2.48	Disagreed	2.43	Disagreed

9.	Digital Rights and Freedom Bill, although not yet enacted into law, it seeks to protect the digital rights of Nigerians, promoting freedom of expression and privacy online	2.01	Disagreed	2.32	Disagreed
10.	National e-Government Master Plan aimed at digitizing government operations and services; making them more accessible to citizens and promoting digital literacy and inclusion	2.44	Disagreed	2.40	Disagreed
	Cluster Mean	2.44		2.47	

Table 2 shows that items 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9 and 10 are remarked, 'disagreed' due to the fact that the mean ratings of each item ranges from 2.01 to 2.49 which are less than 2.5 needed for acceptance. It means the extent of implementation of digital inclusion policies identified on items 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9 and 10 is low. Some of the items that lecturers perceived to be implemented to a low extent include but are not limited to: National Digital Learning Policy which is meant for policy direction and general guidelines, digital learning platforms development, local digital content provisioning, infrastructure and access devices, and capacity building; Universal Service Provision Fund (USPF) aimed at facilitating the achievement of national policy goals for universal access and service to ICTs in rural, unserved, and underserved areas in Nigeria, and Digital Financial Services Policy aimed at bringing unserved and underserved Nigerians into the formal financial sector through technology. On the other hand, respondents affirmed that the digital inclusion policies on item 1, 4 and 7 to a high extent are implemented. This is ascertained by the fact that the items are remarked, 'agreed'. The items are: National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) which was launched to transform Nigeria into a leading digital economy; National Broadband Plan aimed at increasing broadband penetration across the country; ensuring that more Nigerians have access to high-speed internet, which is crucial for digital inclusion, and NITDA Digital State Initiative with focus on training Nigerian youths aged 16 to 40 in digital literacy and skills, covering areas such as digital marketing, productivity tools, and content

creation.

Research Question 3: What are the challenges limiting digital inclusion policies from being effectively implemented in universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean ratings of lecturers on the challenges limiting digital inclusion policies from being effectively implemented in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

S/N	Items: The challenges faced in implementing digital inclusion policies	Male (n=678)		Female (n=678)	
		Mean	Remark	Mean	Remark
1.	Limited internet and power infrastructure leading to many rural areas being underserved; making digital inclusion difficult to achieve	2.61	Agreed	2.81	Agreed
2.	High cost of internet and devices as the cost of smartphones, computers, and internet services remains high, limiting access for low-income individuals	2.72	Agreed	2.68	Agreed
3.	Low digital literacy levels as many Nigerians, especially in rural areas, lack the necessary digital skills to fully participate in the digital economy	2.70	Agreed	2.72	Agreed
4.	Inadequacy of policy implementation and coordination as poor execution, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and lack of coordination between government agencies tend to slow down progress	2.72	Agreed	2.68	Agreed
5.	Cybersecurity and data privacy concerns as weak cybersecurity laws and awareness make people hesitant to engage in digital platforms due to fears of fraud, scams, and data breaches	2.81	Agreed	2.67	Agreed
6.	Limited Local Content and Indigenous Language Support as lack of digital resources in local languages and culturally relevant content makes it harder for some populations to engage with digital tools	2.69	Agreed	2.76	Agreed
7.	Gender and socioeconomic barriers as women and marginalized groups often face additional obstacles, including cultural norms, financial constraints, and limited access to digital education	2.66	Agreed	2.79	Agreed

8.	Unstable government policies and regulatory uncertainty as frequent changes in regulations and lack of long-term digital policy commitments hinder investment in digital inclusion initiatives	2.70	Agreed	2.67	Agreed
9.	Inadequacy of public awareness and engagement as many people are unaware of existing digital inclusion policies and programs, reducing participation and impact	2.67	Agreed	2.60	Agreed
10.	Corruption and mismanagement of funds as funds designated for digital inclusion projects are often misused leading to partial or non-implementation of the said projects	2.75	Agreed	2.67	Agreed
	Cluster Mean	2.70		2.71	

Table 3 shows that the average ratings of all the items are remarked, 'agreed', meaning the respondents perceived them to be noticeable challenges. It is understood that the mean values for the various items range from 2.61 to 2.81, which are above the 2.5 benchmark for acceptance of a research item in the study. From results on the table, the challenges faced in implementing digital inclusion policies include: limited internet and power infrastructure leading to many rural areas being underserved; making digital inclusion difficult to achieve; high cost of internet and devices as the cost of smartphones, computers, and internet services remains high, limiting access for low-income individuals; low digital literacy levels as many Nigerians, especially in rural areas, lack the necessary digital skills to fully participate in the digital economy; inadequacy of policy implementation and coordination as poor execution, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and lack of coordination between government agencies tend to slow down progress; cybersecurity and data privacy concerns as weak cybersecurity laws and awareness make people hesitant to engage in digital platforms due to fears of fraud, scams, and data breaches; limited Local Content and Indigenous Language Support as lack of digital resources in local languages and culturally relevant content makes it harder for some populations to engage with digital tools; gender and socioeconomic barriers as women and marginalized groups often

face additional obstacles, including cultural norms, financial constraints, and limited access to digital education; unstable government policies and regulatory uncertainty as frequent changes in regulations and lack of long-term digital policy commitments hinder investment in digital inclusion initiatives; inadequacy of public awareness and engagement as many people are unaware of existing digital inclusion policies and programs, reducing participation and impact, and corruption and mismanagement of funds as funds designated for digital inclusion projects are often misused leading to partial or non-implementation of the said projects.

Discussions of Results

The study reported that the extent of awareness of the existence of the following digital inclusion policies is low: National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS); National Digital Learning Policy; Universal Service Provision Fund (USPF); National Broadband Plan; Digital Rights and Freedom Bill, and National e-Government Master Plan while the extent of awareness of the existence of Digital Financial Services Policy; National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act, 2007; ICT in Education Policy, and NITDA Digital State Initiative as part of digital inclusion policies is high. One thing is to come up with promising strategies, another thing is to make the policy popular and appreciated by the people, and this can be made possible through widespread awareness programs that could reach every category of end users seamlessly. The finding is related to Masimbe (2019), who argued that Nigeria as one of the developing nations of the world still has a lot of her citizens residing in rural and remote area which they lack access to some information of emerging policies of the government, resulting in lack of awareness of the same. Without doubt, the level of awareness of the existence of most digital oriented policies in Nigeria is low, even in the urban areas where people get carried away by pressure from economic realities.

The study also revealed that the extent of implementation of the following digital inclusion policies is low: National Digital Learning Policy; Universal Service Provision Fund (USPF); Digital Financial Services Policy; National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Act, 2007; ICT in Education Policy; Digital Rights and Freedom Bill, and National e-Government Master Plan. In consonance with the finding, Nwana (2022) argued that no matter how promising a digitally-driven policy might be, if not effectively implemented, it will not make the needed impact, and poor implementation of policies has been a major challenge in developing nations, including Nigeria. For instance, while the National Digital Economy Policy Strategy 2020-2030 targets 70% broadband penetration in 4 years, internet penetration in Nigeria stood at 40% in January 2024, which could be a setback to the target of the policy. On the other hand, the extent of implementation of the following digital inclusion policies were reported to be high: National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) which was launched to transform Nigeria into a leading digital economy; National Broadband Plan aimed at increasing broadband penetration across the country; ensuring that more Nigerians have access to high-speed internet, which is crucial for digital inclusion, and NITDA Digital State Initiative with focus on training Nigerian youths aged 16 to 40 in digital literacy and skills, covering areas such as digital marketing, productivity tools, and content creation. This is in tandem with Oladipupo and Abdulazeez (2024) who pointed out that policies efforts are being made by government at implementing some strategies that would support digitalization in Nigeria without limits, for instance the National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy. Policies such as NDEPS, if adequately implemented could be the game-changer in the Nigerian digital landscape.

The study further reported the challenges faced in implementing digital inclusion policies include: limited internet and power infrastructure leading to many rural areas being underserved; making digital inclusion difficult to achieve; high cost of internet and devices as the cost of smartphones, computers, and internet services remains high, limiting access for low-income individuals; low digital literacy levels as many Nigerians, especially in rural areas, lack the necessary digital skills to fully participate in the digital economy; inadequacy of policy implementation and coordination as poor execution, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and lack of coordination between government agencies tend to slow down progress; cybersecurity and data privacy concerns as weak cybersecurity laws and awareness make people hesitant to engage in digital platforms due to fears of fraud, scams, and data breaches; limited Local Content and Indigenous Language Support as lack of digital resources in local languages and culturally relevant content makes it harder for some populations to engage with digital tools; gender and socioeconomic barriers as women and marginalized groups often face additional obstacles, including cultural norms, financial constraints, and limited access to digital education; unstable government policies and regulatory uncertainty as frequent changes in regulations and lack of long-term digital policy commitments hinder investment in digital inclusion initiatives; inadequacy of public awareness and engagement as many people are unaware of existing digital inclusion policies and programs, reducing participation and impact, and corruption and mismanagement of funds as funds designated for digital inclusion projects are often misused leading to partial or non-implementation of the said projects. Similarly, Akinniyi, Erinsakin and Emma-Ayire (2021) cited corruption and misappropriation of funds intended for ICT programmes, procurement fraud, and bribery can hinder effective implementation of digital learning initiatives as noticeable limitation to digital inclusion. Also, Oladipupo and Abdulazeez

(2024) observed that public schools, which cater to the majority (over 80%) of students' higher education, is often confronted with lack well-equipped computer laboratories; limited number of qualified ICT instructors; limited internet connectivity; unreliable power supply (Jacob, Somadina & Olatunde-Aiyedun, 2021); high cost of digital devices (Masimbe, 2019), and unethical practices, hence impeding the effective delivery of digital literacy programmes.

Conclusion

Digital inclusion is a fundamental aspect of modern society, enabling individuals to fully participate in the digital economy and access essential services. Ensuring widespread digital inclusion requires comprehensive policies with adequate publicities as to the scope of the policies as well as how it will be effectively implemented. Undoubtedly, implementation of digital inclusion policies requires functional supportive resources, including skilled trainers and instructors, dependable power supply, objective utilization of allocated funds for operations and acquisitions, steady and sustainable internet infrastructure, so as to make technology accessible and affordable for all. Unfortunately, the study revealed that the extent of awareness and implementation of digital inclusion policies in universities in Nigeria is low. Likewise, the expected supportive infrastructure and skilled manpower to implement the policies are short in supply, thereby making it difficult for the goals of digital inclusivity to be achieved. This is a big setback in pursuit of the digital inclusion limitlessly.

Recommendations

In line with findings of the study, the following recommendations were put forward:

1. There should be comprehensive and sustained awareness programs about the various digital inclusion policies in Nigeria. The awareness should be well-planned, organized and constantly carried out in a viral manner to enlighten and ensure the public is abreast with everything the policies stand for. Doing this will equip and turn the attention of the public to the digital inclusivity goals being pursued, thereby improving their awareness about the policies.
2. There should be objectivity when it comes to implementing policies, especially when it is for the public's interest, like the case of digital inclusion. Being objective in this situation means being transparent, not being biased, not allowing favouritism or any corrupt practice to meddle with the implementation of the digital inclusion policies. It is only when digital inclusion policies are effectively implemented that the benefits can be earned and appreciated.
3. There should be provision of required supportive infrastructure and resources, such as skilled trainers, functional internet facilities, steady power supply, adequate funds for procurement, distribution and operations of digital inclusion programmes, and continuity in programme implementations. With all the requirements functionally put in place, it will be easier to achieve the goals of digital inclusion in Nigeria, including South-South universities.

References

- Ajayi, F. A., & Udeh, C. A. (2024). Review of workforce upskilling initiatives for emerging technologies in IT. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 6(4), 1119-1137.
- Akinniyi, A. J., Erinsakin, O. A., & Emma-Ayire, S. O. (2021). Corruption in the Nigerian education sector: Causes and remedies. *KIU Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 1-13.
- Akinyemi, A., & Ofem, C. (2019). Digital skills and research productivity in Nigerian universities. *Journal of Higher Education Studies*, 12(3), 45-61.
- Arthur-Mensah, N. (2020). Bridging the industry–education skills gap for human resource development. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 52(2), 93-103.
- Federal Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy (2023). *National digital literacy framework*. Abuja: National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA).
- Jacob, O. N., Somadina, O. I., & Olatunde-Aiyedun, T. G. (2021). *Deployment of ICT Facilities by Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) During Covid-19 in Nigeria: Challenges and way Forward*. Ibadan: University Press.
- Lombardi, M. (2023). *Digital economy and digital divide*. In *Global Handbook of Inequality* (pp. 1-27). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Masimbe, C. (2019). *Mobile internet access and affordability among youth in South Africa: rethinking universal service and access in the age of digital mobility*. (Doctoral dissertation)
- Nwana, S. (2022). Challenges in the application of e-learning by secondary school teachers in Anambra state, Nigeria. *African Journal of Teacher Education*, 1(2), 1-9.
- Nworgu, B.G. (2015). *Education research: Basic issues and methodology (3rd ed.)*. Enugu: University Trust Publishers.
- Nwosu, B. (2020). Barriers to digital inclusion in Nigerian higher education: Challenges and policy implications. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 14(2), 112-127.
- OECD (2021). *Digitalisation in higher education: Trends and challenges*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.
- Oladipupo, B. & Abdulazeez, O. A. (2024). Digital literacy and skills development in Nigeria: Policies, barriers and recommendations. *Journal of African Innovation & Advanced Studies (JAIAS)*, 2(5), 133-150.
- Tanny, T. F. (2018). *Survey research design*. Retrieved from <http://slideshare.net/TahminaTanny/survey-research-design>, on 10 July, 2023.